

Title: Critical Review - The Foreign Policy of the United States of America during the Terms of Harry S. Truman (1945–1953) Truman, Containment, and Arctic Geopolitics.

Abstract:

This critical review addresses the broad lines of United States foreign policy during President Harry S. Truman's tenure from 1945 to 1952. A political-diplomatic chronology of the United States was used, beginning with Roosevelt's death and Truman's succession and running through Eisenhower's appointment at the end of 1952. The bibliographic references that guided this review—Pierre Melandri's *La politique extérieure des Etats-Unis de 1945 à nos jours* (1982) and Gary B. Nash et al., *The American People: Creating a Nation and a Society* (1998)—were subject to analytical reading and their positions compared with other authors consulted using these two works as starting points.

Keywords

Political Studies; United States Foreign Policy; Truman; Cold War; Containment, Arctic Geopolitics

Introduction

In the early twenty-first century, the foreign policy concepts forged under President Harry S. Truman—containment, alliance-building, and the militarization of U.S. global commitments—continue to shape American behavior in seemingly distant arenas such as the Arctic and Greenland. The renewed U.S. push to acquire or otherwise assert stronger control over Greenland, openly advocated by President Donald Trump in 2019 and again since his return to office in 2025, illustrates the enduring relevance of Cold War logics of security, geography, and ideology in contemporary American statecraft. The main themes analysed in this review concern the origins of the Cold War, the Soviet–American ideological conflict as the basis of the policy of “containment” (i.e., confinement) in its various dimensions, for example economic and military, and the containment policy before and after 1950— i.e., during Truman's first and second terms. The review attempts to analyse the extent to which Truman's actions shaped the orientation of U.S. foreign policy and which conditions may have influenced his positions. By situating Truman's foreign policy within its Cold War context and tracing its core ideas—containment, forward defense, and the linking of security to economic and ideological competition—this review provides a framework for understanding contemporary U.S. ambitions in

Greenland and the wider Arctic. The analysis suggests that current American discourse about Greenland as a strategic asset and as a necessary buffer against rival powers in the Arctic echoes earlier Truman-era assumptions about the necessity of preponderant U.S. power to secure a favorable world order.

Method:

This article is conceived as a critical review of secondary literature on U.S. foreign policy during the Truman presidency, rather than as an archival study based on new primary sources. Its primary aim is interpretive: to compare classic accounts of containment, such as those by Melandri and Nash et al., with revisionist and post-revisionist perspectives in order to reassess Truman's role in defining the early Cold War order. The method followed in this review was analytical reading, interpretation, comparative evaluation, and consequent critical commentary. Sources were selected on the basis of three criteria: (1) their status as canonical syntheses of U.S. foreign policy in the early Cold War (for example Nash et al., 1998; Melandri, 1982); (2) their explicit focus on Truman as a decision-maker or on containment as a strategic doctrine (for example Gaddis, 1978; Acheson, 1969); and (3) their usefulness for juxtaposing traditional Cold War narratives with later revisionist critiques. This strategy allows the review to move beyond purely descriptive chronology and instead reconstruct competing interpretive traditions about Truman's foreign policy. Although the empirical focus is 1945–1953, the article also mobilizes selected recent scholarship and public documentation on contemporary U.S. policy toward the Arctic and Greenland, in order to illustrate how Truman-era categories still inform the language and logic of American policy-makers. This limited extension into present-day debates serves heuristic purposes and does not claim to offer a comprehensive analysis of Arctic security policy.

Results

The general lines that defined U.S. foreign policy during Truman's presidency are simultaneously linked to the origins of the Cold War in the post-World War II period, the policy of containment both economically and militarily enabled by the emergence of the United States as the leading power, and the ways in which that power was used to sustain American ambitions. As Gary B. Nash et al. (1998) explain: "The United States emerged from WWII more powerful than any other nation ever before. Now it sought to use that might to achieve the kind of order that could sustain American aims. American policy makers, following in Woodrow Wilson's footsteps, hoped to spread the values of liberty, equality and democracy that provided the underpinning of the American Dream. They assumed that they could furnish the stability that post-war reconstruction required. They did not always recognise that they considered universal truths were rooted in specific historical circumstances in their own country and might not flourish elsewhere." On the other hand, a

revisionist reading by Pierre Melandri (1982), who at the time preferred to emphasise the external positioning of the United States in the figure of Truman and his more resolute attitude after the rather fruitless Yalta Conference (Feb. 1945) compared to his predecessor Roosevelt, clarifies: “La mort de Roosevelt (12 avril de 1945) ouvrit la Maison Blanche à un homme décidé à placer ses relations avec le Kremlin sur un autre terrain: celui de la puissance, plutôt que d’une aveugle confiance. L’interruption brutale du prêt-bail (mai 1945) traduisait, quoi qu’il ait pu en être dit, sa volonté d’utiliser le pouvoir financier des Etats-Unis pour faire pression sur la Russie. Et l’insertion dans la Charte des Nations Unies des articles 51 et 52 autorisant la constitution des pactes régionaux marqua la détermination de Washington d’éviter toute intervention étrangère dans la zone définie par la doctrine de Monroe.” (Melandri 1982: 57) We must also note the economic motivations underlying U.S. foreign policy after World War II— namely, the need for international markets to absorb industrial products as soon as the war ended, which required breaking down barriers imposed by the Soviet Union and other nations (Gary B. Nash et al., 1998: 949). In the critical appraisal below, the costs and scale of military/defense programs borne by the U.S economy are also addressed.

Discussion:

As noted in the subject description, U.S. foreign policy during Truman’s presidency developed alongside the Cold War and can be ideologically explained by the antagonism of worldviews opposing the Soviet Union, which pursued the communist utopia, and the United States, which sought leadership through free enterprise. However, ideological explanation alone does not exhaust the origins of the Cold War nor fully account for the American decision to pursue economic and military containment of the Soviet Union.

Indeed, the USSR’s objectives in the postwar period—the fear of invasion on its western flanks, its traditional insecurity, and attempts to exert influence over countries sympathetic to Soviet policy— explain a large part of American reticence in their foreign policy (ibid.: 950).

At this point U.S. containment had not yet become radical; Truman had not yet articulated his ideas of greater confrontation, and it was still one year before the “Truman Doctrine.” Above all, the Kremlin could still cooperate on a future invasion of Japan, as Melandri notes: “Truman revint très vite à une politique de conciliation. Il était trop inexpérimenté, en effet, pour rompre brutalement avec la politique de son prédécesseur, trop conscient des limites des pressions économiques sur une Union Soviétique désormais à même de se servir directement sur les territoires occupés et trop pénétré de l’importance que ses militaires accordaient à la coopération du Kremlin à la future invasion du Japon.”

In Europe there is near unanimity among authors on the triggering effect of Poland for U.S. policy at the end of World War II: the United States expected to see in Poland the emergence of a representative regime along Western lines, contrary to Russia’s demand to exert influence there. As Melandri points out, the Yalta Conference failed to resolve this: “Staline, il est vrai, avait pu s’étonner de l’extrême intérêt soudain manifesté

par les Etats-Unis par la Pologne. C'était oublier que Pearl Harbour avait développé la conviction que rien de ce qui se passait dans le monde n'était indifférent à Washington." (ibid.: 57) Indeed, with Truman's arrival in power, U.S. foreign policy became more inflexible. At the April 1945 meeting with Soviet Foreign Minister Vyacheslav Molotov, the American president demanded the establishment of democracy in Poland—a demand received skeptically by Russia, evidenced in the exchange between Truman and Molotov: "Truman insisted on Russia acquiescence. Truman later recalled that when Molotov protested, 'I have never been talked to like that in my life,' he himself retorted bluntly, 'Carry out your agreements and you won't get talked to like that.' Such bluntness contributed to the deterioration of Soviet–American relations." (Gary B. Nash et al.) Economic pressure on the USSR also contributed to the deterioration of Soviet–American relations. In fact, the United States was more committed to restoring prosperity than to eliminating Russia's abusive influence. Truman received a Soviet request for aid of one billion dollars and intended to accept on the condition that Russia join the world trading system; Stalin disagreed and launched his five-year plan (ibid.: 953).

Rhetorical attacks intensified and capitalism and communism collided in Stalin's words, as reported by the U.S. Supreme Court: "Stalin's speech was a stark and ominous statement that worried the West. Supreme Court Justice William O. Douglas called it 'a declaration of World War III'" (ibid.: 953). In these terms the Cold War is declared (a "Third World War" in the view of several authors), and the response did not come from the Americans but rather from Churchill, who had long suspected the Soviets, declaring in Fulton, Missouri in 1946, in Truman's presence: "From Stettin in the Baltic to Trieste in the Adriatic an iron curtain has descended across the continent." To combat this threat it was urgent that a platform of English-speaking peoples watch and contain

Soviet designs. Thus emerged the policy of "containment," which distributed itself differently before and after the 1950s—a distinction explored in the following sections. When America's turn toward containment was publicly declared to halt Soviet advance, Truman aimed to establish a kind of Pax Americana. As George F. Kennan explained (Melandri, 1982): "En réalité, les possibilités américaines ne sont nullement limitées à une politique de coups d'arrêt, assortis de vœux pieux pour les Etats-Unis d'influencer par leurs actions les développements ultérieurs, à la fois à l'intérieur de l'URSS et à travers le mouvement communiste international qui détermine largement la politique russe."

George Kennan was responsible for formulating the containment policy, popularised by his telegram in 1946 while serving as the U.S. ambassador in Moscow, where he argued that the Soviet–American dispute originated in the Kremlin's neurotic view of foreign affairs, rooted in a traditional Russian instinct of insecurity. This attitude was not aimed primarily at America but rather at perpetuating autocratic rule in Russia; even if American diplomacy adapted, Russia's position would remain fanatical and therefore had to be opposed firmly (Gary B. Nash). Extreme as it may be, Kennan's analysis had a significant effect in Washington and elevated his

influence within the State Department. Kennan also published a famous article under the pseudonym "Mr. X" in *Foreign Affairs*, reinforcing his analysis of Russian foreign policy: "Moves inexorably along the prescribed path, like a persistent toy automobile wound up and headed in a given direction, stopping only when it meets with some unanswerable force." [1]

The fading of earlier hopes placed in the United Nations also contributed to U.S. policy of containment. Secretary of the Navy James V. Forrestal warned in 1946: "Either we succeed in making the UN work, or we will be faced with a world in which we will have to maintain a military strength sufficiently overwhelming so that no future aggressor would have any doubt." [2] Hopes for a purely diplomatic (nonmilitary) solution died when, a year later in 1947, a vote on national security expressed the desire to integrate a military dimension into American international relations, and the CIA was established. Reviewing American diplomacy through the actions of Truman and Kennan (whose influence seems considerable despite some authors emphasising external conditions), the "Truman Doctrine" emerged as the first major application of the containment policy. The Doctrine initially sought to respond to conditions in the eastern Mediterranean—an area the United States had never previously considered vital to national security. The Soviet Union at the time pressured Turkey for shared control of the Dardanelles (the passage from the Black Sea to the Mediterranean), while a civil war in Greece had produced communist elements challenging the monarchy and British support. In 1947 the British ceased military and economic assistance to Turkey and Greece. The question remained: would the Americans fill that vacuum?

In Truman's words, his doctrine motivated the request for financial aid to those countries presented to Congress on 12 March 1947: "I believe that it must be the policy of the United States to support free peoples who are resisting subjugation by armed minorities or by outside pressures." (Gary B. Nash et al.) Critics expressed doubts about the Doctrine; Walter Lippmann was notably critical of Truman: "The Truman Doctrine was a strategic monstrosity that could embroil the U.S. in disputes around the world." Nevertheless, Congress approved the aid request. Following congressional approval, three steps guided the containment policy before 1950 alongside the Truman Doctrine: the Marshall Plan, NATO, and the NSC-68 document. The role of these elements in shaping containment during Truman's years is considered below. It is now known that difficulties in resolving the German question, and the lack of progress following the Moscow Conference in 1947, convinced Secretary of State George C. Marshall to commission Kennan, as head of the Policy Planning Staff, to prepare a plan that would become the most clarifying version of containment. The United States committed to helping Europe rebuild so that

European nations would become prosperous partners free from communism. The Marshall Plan consisted of three steps: 1) extensive aid for the reconstruction of Western Europe, where unstable

governments risked opening the way to communism (see Annex 1, supporting map 1, p. 15), for example Italy and France; Marshall described it thus: “The Marshall Plan and the Truman Doctrine were two halves of the same walnut.” 2) Strengthen European economies to create prosperous markets for the United States, agreeing to provide \$17 billion in aid over four years to sixteen cooperating nations. 3) Reintegration of Germany, which Marshall deemed indispensable when addressing Congress: “The restoration of Europe involves the restoration of Germany. Without a revival of German production there can be no revival of Europe’s economy. But we must be very careful to see that a revived Germany cannot again threaten the European community.” (Ibid.: 955) Although the plan’s economic success was largely assured, ideologically and militarily the Marshall Plan formalized the rupture between the U.S. and Russia: Melandri notes that “Truman had explicitly requested economic and military aid for Greece and Turkey,” and, in 1948, with the Selective Service Act and renewed military recruitment, the rupture with the USSR became clear alongside Soviet measures such as the creation of the Cominform and the 1948 Prague coup. The next step in the containment strategy was the creation of a military alliance of twelve European nations—NATO—committing all members that an attack on any one would be considered an attack on all and would trigger appropriate force. It is noteworthy that the Senate had long opposed such pacts but this time approved establishing the United States, for the first time since the American Revolution, into a military treaty tying it to Europe (Gary B. Nash et al.: 956).

The third pre-1950 element of containment, NSC-68, was spurred by two developments: the success of communists in the Chinese civil war and the Soviet detonation of an atomic device. These developments prompted Truman to request a reassessment of U.S. foreign and defense policy. The National Security Council’s NSC-68 would shape American policy for the next twenty years. For the executive, NSC-68 expressed that if the United States wished to meet the Soviet challenge it would have to increase its defense budget, which by 1950 rose from \$13 billion and would increase year by year to a peak of \$50 billion (see Annex 1, Support Chart 1 on defense expenditures, p. 17). The second phase of containment after 1950 was marked by various “situations of force” and localised conflicts: Korea; the Chinese Revolution; turbulence in the Middle East; revolts in Latin America (considered the United States’ backyard); and above all generalised rearmament. Containment became more rigid when Dean Acheson, Truman’s new Secretary of State, warned in 1950: “We must press forward in our determination to create situations of strength in the free world, because it is the only basis on which a lasting agreement with the Soviet government will be possible.” (Dean Acheson, 1969: 378) As a consequence of this new posture, Truman considered rearmament a priority and ordered the development of the hydrogen bomb (31 Jan 1950), noting that while the USSR was spending 13.6% of its GDP on rearmament, the United States spent less than 7%, and committed henceforth to reach up to 20%.

The Korean War further entrenched U.S. involvement in Asian affairs. Formerly under Japanese rule after its defeat, Korea sought independence; allies temporarily divided Korea along the 38th parallel, with Soviet troops stationed in the north and American troops in the south. On 25 June 1950 North Korea invaded the South with Soviet-supplied tanks. On 30 June Truman ordered MacArthur to provide air support and assist South Korean leader Syngman Rhee. From then on, U.S. foreign policy assumed a strongly military dimension: arms assistance to allied countries—long contested—became a priority. Domestically and internationally, the CIA was granted authority over “special operations” seen as necessary to promote American interests.

Another geostrategic area, the Middle East, assumed enormous importance for industrialised nations because of oil demand. After World War II, the United Kingdom and the United States had withdrawn their troops from Iran; the Soviet Union, however, did not follow suit, claiming that agreements had not been honoured and demanding oil concessions, provoking fierce American opposition. In Palestine, Truman recognised the state of Israel fifteen minutes after its proclamation. This did not resolve animosities: Arab states attacked Israel, which nevertheless prevailed and increased the territory allocated by the United Nations. In this balance of forces, the United States—closely linked to Israel—attempted simultaneously to maintain ties with Arab oil-producing states (Gary B. Nash et al.: 962). This turbulent region would later be the site of many developments and conflicts during the Eisenhower administration.

The Cold War also affected relations with Latin America, long regarded by the United States as its “backyard.” Activities labeled communist—such as in Guatemala—led to CIA involvement in arming guerrillas to overthrow legitimately elected governments. Relations with Cuba were embargoed both diplomatically and economically after Fidel Castro’s rise and his turn toward Soviet support (Ibid.:964). The final “situation of force” analysed in Truman’s foreign policy concerns nuclear weapons and their influence on the Cold War and the resultant containment policy. Containment would not have reached the scale it did without the crucial factor of nuclear weapons. U.S. development of nuclear arms had been discovered by the KGB shortly after World War II, yet the United States understood it could not control Russia solely through this element. Although authors are almost unanimous, it is important to highlight Truman’s legislative actions, such as the Atomic Energy Act, which supervised all nuclear activities and authorised them domestically and internationally. Nuclear proliferation, which was widespread in the United States, excited rather than horrified many. Everything changed when scientists concluded that nuclear explosions had occurred within the USSR. Nobel laureate Harold C. Urey summarised the mood: “There is only one thing worse than one nation having the atomic bomb, that’s two nations having it.”

In 1953 Truman authorised the development of the hydrogen bomb—potentially more devastating than the atomic bomb. Developments in this field led to genuine “massive retaliation.” The United States was willing to use nuclear weapons against the communist threat, and the buildup of a nuclear arsenal revitalised the

armaments industry and posed not only strategic and ideological challenges but economic ones as well. For more than thirty years the world lived on the brink of massive destruction, encapsulated by Secretary of State John Foster Dulles' dictum: "The ability to get to the verge without getting into war is the necessary art." (Gary B. Nash et al.: 968) The development of the Cold War affected not only foreign policy (the focus here) but also domestic politics. Evidence of this includes Truman's Loyalty Program and investigations by the House Un-American Activities Committee (HUAC), which convinced many Americans that a communist threat existed within the United States. Finally, McCarthy's "witch hunt" grew in influence as Republicans gained control of the Senate and his power increased.

Contemporary Arctic Geopolitics

The contemporary U.S. insistence on acquiring or otherwise dominating Greenland suggests that the logic of containment has been geographically displaced, not overcome. Greenland's location astride North Atlantic and Arctic sea lanes, its proximity to Russian military activity through the GIUK gap, and its growing relevance for missile-defense and early-warning systems all echo Truman-era assumptions that security depends on controlling the outer perimeter of the North Atlantic and Eurasia. Since 2019, and even more assertively after 2025, President Donald Trump has framed Greenland as essential to U.S. national security and has repeatedly floated the possibility of purchasing, annexing, or otherwise bringing the island under American sovereignty, provoking sharp resistance from both Denmark and Greenlandic authorities. This discourse portrays Greenland not primarily as a self-governing community but as a strategic asset in a renewed great-power competition with Russia and China in the Arctic, in ways reminiscent of how Truman officials conceived Greece, Turkey, and Korea as peripheral yet indispensable fronts in the global struggle against Soviet expansion. The continuity is not simply rhetorical. The current U.S. emphasis on strengthening military infrastructure in and around Greenland—including existing facilities such as Thule Air Base and proposals for expanded surveillance and missile-defense capabilities—reflects a Truman-style belief in the utility of permanent forward deployments to deter adversaries and reassure allies. In this sense, Greenland serves today as both a literal and symbolic outpost of an American security perimeter that was first systematically conceptualized in the early Cold War. At the same time, the Greenland controversy underlines important differences between the early Cold War environment and the present. Unlike the relatively hierarchical alliance structures of Truman's time, today's governance of Greenland involves a complex interplay between the United States, Denmark, and a self-governing Greenlandic government that mobilizes international law, indigenous rights, and environmental concerns to resist unilateral American initiatives. This multi-actor setting complicates any straightforward application of containment logic and highlights the limits of viewing twenty-first-century Arctic politics through a purely Cold War lens.

Conclusion

Whether we emphasise Truman's individual political agency as a statesman or accept postwar constraints as the major influence on U.S. foreign policy, we must also judge Truman as a product of the American Democratic Party (Bernstein, 1970). Like Roosevelt, Truman believed that the federal government had responsibilities—particularly social ones—to ensure the welfare of all Americans. As Gary B. Nash et al. stated: "Truman was, in many ways, an old-style Democratic politician, schooled and supported by Missouri's Democratic machine, who hoped to use his authority to benefit the middle-class and working-class Americans, who made up his political base."

The question posed at the outset of this review—about the origins of the Cold War and its impact on American foreign policy—receives near-unanimous interpretation among the various authors: in perspective, the Cold War had a profound impact on American society in the decades following World War II. Tensions grew as the United States and the Soviet Union engaged in an acrimonious dispute that, in the end, dominated international relations for more than 50 years. During the period considered here, political commentators defended the American posture as courageous in the face of communist pressure. Yet revisionist scholarship of the 1960s and 1970s criticised American leadership, accusing the United States of failing to understand Soviet necessities (Robert J. Donovan, 1977: 56).

The persistence of Truman-era assumptions is perhaps most visible today in the Arctic, where the U.S. ambition to secure Greenland mirrors earlier efforts to lock in American strategic predominance in Europe, the Mediterranean, and East Asia. By reading the Greenland crisis through the lens of containment, it becomes clear that contemporary debates over sovereignty, bases, and resources in the Arctic are not an historical aberration but an extension of patterns established during Truman's presidency, now refracted through new environmental, legal, and normative constraints.

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Video/Conference <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cuxeq78sBmM> (This video informed the production of the document, to understand what lessons and perspectives may be drawn today from the Cold War and the Containment policy of the 1950s.) Melvyn P. Leffler is the Edward R. Stettinius Professor of American History at the University of Virginia. Oct 16, 2008 at the University of Texas at Austin, LBJ School of Public Affairs. Melvyn P. Leffler served as Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences at UVA from 1997–2001 and as president of the Society of Historians of American Foreign Relations. He has been a Fellow at the Norwegian Nobel Institute, the Woodrow Wilson International Center and the United States Institute of Peace. He served in the Carter administration's Office of the Secretary of Defense as a Council on Foreign Relations Fellow. His book *A Preponderance of Power* won the Bancroft Prize in 1993. This presentation is part of the Strauss Center's International Security Speaker Series, which features leading scholars and policy practitioners